

Smart Message Feed evaluation

About a month ago we introduced the [Smart Feed Bot](link) that provides a personalized digest of messages in public Space channels. It is meant to help Space users navigate through all the messages without missing vital information.

With this questionnaire we want to evaluate the quality of the Smart Feed, and to learn how we could improve it. We keep all survey results in a confidential way, we will make anonymized summaries out of them and may use them in the paper. Once the research is over we will delete everything – so that no personal data will be ever used.

Thank you for your participation!

Message evaluation

Below you will find your personal feed containing messages from the last three days. Please, evaluate those messages via like/dislike. There are no strict criteria, only your perception of whether you like this message suggestion and if you would like to see it in your feed.

(1) Please, evaluate recommendations that @[AUTHOR] sent you in Space.

Like/Dislike choice for each message

(2) What did you like about those recommendations?

Text box

(3) What did you dislike about those recommendations?

Text box

(4) Overall, how useful do you find the idea of Smart Message Feed. Would you use it?

- *Yes, I would definitely like to use it. (37%)*
- *I would give it a try. (56%)*
- *I do not think I would use it but maybe someone could change my mind. (7%)*
- *I absolutely do not need it. **END OF SURVEY** (0%)*

Smart Message Feed

(1) In general, what kind of messages would you like to see in your Feed?

- *From channels you are subscribed to*
- *From channels you are not subscribed to*
- *Messages you were mentioned in (but haven't reacted or answered)*
- *Work-/project-related*
- *Other teams work*
- *Social (birthdays, events, etc.)*
- *Other [text box]*

(2) In general, what kind of messages would you strongly dislike to see in your Feed?

- *From channels you are subscribed to*
- *From channels you are not subscribed to*
- *Messages you were mentioned in (but haven't reacted or answered)*
- *Work-/project-related*
- *Other teams work*
- *Social (birthdays, events, etc.)*
- *Other [text box]*

(3) How often would you like to receive the Smart Message Feed?

- *Every day*
- *Every working day*
- *Once a week*
- *Once a month*

(4) How many recommendations by default would you like to receive?

1 to 10 linear scale

(5) Below, you can see a screenshot with all the available commands in the Smart Feed Bot. Are there any other commands you would like to be added?

Text box

Thank you for your response!

If you are not yet subscribed to the Smart Feed Bot but would like to try it out, here is the link. If you have any questions or suggestions, please reach out to [AUTHOR].

Would you like to add anything on how the Smart Feed should work?

Text box